

Co-UDlabs project: collaborative Research Infrastructures research and innovation in the field of urban drainage

COLLABORATIVE URBAN DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES

- CONSORTIUM**
9 partners
7 countries
- DURATION**
4 years
- START-END DATE**
01.05.2021
30.04.2025
- BUDGET**
5 M€

www.co-udlabs.eu

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MOTIVATION

Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) are **critical infrastructures** that directly interface with natural aquatic systems and control and convey urban stormwater and wastewater to treatment facilities. UDS are **crucial for protecting public health**, and for safely manage stormwater, **reducing pollutant's impacts and urban flood risks**.

Main UDS challenges

- Traditional and emergent contaminants pollution through sewer overflows and stormwater spills.
- Aggravated flood risk due to climate crisis and urbanization
- Aging and deteriorating infrastructures.
- Need of Hybrid Green and Grey Infrastructure approach which integrates traditional assets with Sustainable Drainage solutions and smart technologies.

Large Research Infrastructures can accelerate the innovation and research of UDS sector characterized by working in silos and high resistance to change by providing:

- Full-scale or near-full scale platforms** to test and validate innovative solutions
- Improved training and capacity building programmes** of a broadly low-skilled technical community **for the new challenges** of water digitalization and new environmental regulations
- New services and solutions for practitioners and water operators**, from sensors to standardize methods to share information

Co-UDlabs is a H2020-INFRAIA Starting Community project that has developed Europe's first network of RIs in the field of UDS

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TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS PROGRAMME

Co-UDlabs implemented a TNA programme with 3 open calls to its **17 research facilities** covering the full UDS spectrum:

- Urban flooding
- Runoff pollution
- In sewer-processes
- System performance
- Sustainable Drainage Systems (SUDS)
- Assets deterioration
- Digital water solutions

Co-UDlabs access was held in face-to-face (20-60 days duration) and partially remote (5-20 days) access.

Main results

- 31 projects awarded**
- 33% users from industry, wastewater operators and administrations**
- 24% female users**
- 227 users from 26 countries and 122 institutions**

NETWORKING AND BEYOND

- Identification of RIs users and UDS needs to support effective transition to smart and sustainable UDS
- Zenodo community with project deliverables and publications
- Science to Policy actions.
- Workshops organized in international congress
- Webinar series and tailored training actions for industry (online hands-on course) and early researchers (workshops and PhD courses) available at Co-UDlabs youtube channel

Towards UDS community consolidation

Creation of the **UDRAIN WG on large Ris in UDS** – IWA / IAHR Joint Committee of Urban Drainage (JCUD).

Worldwide Atlas of UDS RIs

FAIR Urban Drainage Initiative of JCUD the International WG on Data and Models

JOINT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES: IMPROVING NETWORK SERVICES

Smart Sensing and Monitoring in UDS:

Testing of 8 new emerging sensors. Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox.

- Open access (code and tool) toolbox for UDS sensor calibration, data validation and uncertainty analysis.
- Available in different languages (EN,FR,SP,GE).

New methods for distributed data analysis.

Evaluation of assets and deterioration impacts:

Asset Inspection – evaluation of defects and condition classification.

- Open-source CCTV defect code analysis.
- Asset inventory data, rainfall,.
- Risks assessment.
- Pro-Active inspection maintenance.

Creation of a catalogue of pipe failures in the lab.

Analysing the effect of defects in UDS performance through numerical modelling.

+info: webinar of findings from Co-UDlabs research and where to access them

Improving Resilience and Sustainability UDS:

Better digital twin models.

- Improved DEM
- Runoff Image velocimetry
- Hydrodynamic and pollution transport processes in sewer/surcharge overflows

New sensors for sediment depth estimation.

Towards standard methods to assess long-term performance of SUDS.

- Permeable Pavements
- Green roofs and vegetated

Hydrodynamic and pollution assessment of Sustainable Drainage solutions (SUDS).

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